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“HELD”

There was a time
when the night felt endless
when silence learned my name
before anyone else did.

I was taught early
how pain can live in familiar hands,
how love can forget to protect,
how a child can learn fear
before she learns a prayer.

My body remembers
what my mouth was never allowed to say.
Bruises taught me quiet.
Neglect taught me distance.
And betrayal—
betrayal came wearing blood
and calling itself family.
But I knew there was always
One who saw.

Not the kind of seeing
that looks away.
Not the kind that excuses.

But the kind that counts every tear
even when I didn't know
how to cry out loud.

I have faith that there is one God.
One Creator.
Of the seen
and the unseen.

The God who watched
when no one intervened.
The God who stayed
when escape felt impossible.
I asked Him not just once but thrice,
"If you love me so dearly,
Then, why did You allow these pains to ruin me?"
And He didn't answer with thunder.
He answered with presence.

He stayed.
Through the healing
that took years.
Through the memories
that still knock without warning.
Through the anger
that wanted to turn me into stone.

And somehow
with hands gentler than mine
He taught me forgiveness.
Not forgetting.
Not excusing.
But releasing my grip
on the poison
that was killing me slowly.

I forgave
not because they deserved peace
but because God wanted me free.

I may now still
live between tears and smiles.
But it is no longer hidden.
It is seen.
Held.
Redeemed.

I am still here
not because I was strong,
but because God was.

